

Approaches to Customer Segmentation as a Function of STP Framework

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Abstract—STP (Segmentation, Targeting, and Positioning) has long been used as a marketing framework to assist businesses better understand who their ideal consumers are and how to approach them. The primary premise of this framework is that you should categorise your clients, target each group based on their preferences and habits, and tailor your branding and marketing techniques to fit their needs and expectations. The relevance of customer segmentation as a key function of STP is examined in this article, as well as a variety of ways for segmenting customers using clustering algorithms. Customer segmentation is the practise of grouping customers who have similar behaviours into one group and grouping customers who have distinct patterns into other groups. Two alternative clustering algorithms (k-Means and hierarchical) are implemented to segment customers in this study, and the results are compared. A Python programme was created, and it was trained on a dataset with eight features and 2000 training samples using a standard scaler.

Keywords—STP framework, K-Means clustering and Hierarchical clustering for segmentation, Principal component analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

The benefit of considering customers as an organization's most valuable asset is growing in prominence in today's world. STP marketing is concerned with commercial effectiveness, identifying a company's most important client groups and developing marketing and product positioning strategies for each.

Customer segmentation is one of the STP marketing strategies for analysing customer behaviour and categorisation. Customers with comparable means, objectives, and behaviours are put together into homogeneous segments using clustering techniques. Customer segmentation aids businesses in discovering or disclosing various groups of customers that think and behave differently and have diverse spending and purchasing patterns.

Customers differ in their behaviour, requirements, wants, and qualities, and the primary goal of clustering techniques is to discover distinct customer types and divide the customer base into clusters of similar characteristics, allowing for more efficient target marketing. The purpose of this study is to look into the possibility of using customer

segmentation as an analysis tool inside the STP framework, as well as the use of clustering methodologies to help businesses gain a clearer picture of their valuable customer base. Customer segmentation as a major component of the STP framework is described, as is the process of segmenting consumers using clustering algorithms.

The benefits and drawbacks of the two primary models used in our study, K-Means and Hierarchical Clustering, are examined, as is the possibility of building a hybrid model that outperforms the individual models. There is additional discussion of the available clustering methods for business analysis in the context of consumer segmentation. The STP Framework is an established way for doing customer research and comprehension.

The process of splitting a population, potential or present consumers, into groups with similar characteristics is known as segmentation. This group will have similar purchasing habits. This segment is likely to respond to a variety of marketing initiatives. For example, not everyone favours the same car company. Furthermore, not everyone can afford to buy the same brand. As a result, their purchasing decisions are influenced by their financial status, age, and gender. We might divide our audience into categories, each of which prefers a distinct brand of car, and not just preferences but also buying trends could be standardised for each location. Marketing campaigns may evoke a wide range of responses from different segments. Customers are classified according to demographics (age, gender, religion, family size, and other characteristics), behavioural (consumption, spending, and other criteria), geographic (where and when they work), and psychographic aspects (social, lifestyle, and more).

Targeting is concerned with determining which segments to focus on and evaluating possible revenues from segments. Consider criteria to choose whether to extend to the entire segment or only a portion of the section.

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II. LITERATURE SURVEY

In today's business environment, establishing the customer lifetime value (CLV) of each client has grown more difficult due to the increase in the number of customers purchasing things online. In this article, customer segmentation is used to assess the customer lifetime value for a UK-based company that offers one-of-a-kind gifts. To begin, clients are divided into three groups based on three factors: "Recency," "Frequency," and "Monetary." Anu Gupta Aggarwal [1] is introducing Fuzzy AHP technique. Using this, the variables are then given weight or priority. To better divide consumers into groups, Xixi He and Chen Li develop a three-dimensional customer segmentation model based on customer lifetime value, customer pleasure, and customer activity in this article. The essential variables are provided by the RFM model, the Kano model, and the BG/NBD model. The customer segmentation model splits consumers into ten groups and assigns different marketing methods to each of them, allowing organisations to maximise profits.

Jianxin Bi [1] proposed for categorising customers based on their insurance Customer Risk Contribution matrix using data mining techniques such as clustering and classification. A Clementine-based segmentation management technique is proposed. Insurance firms should use the insurance customer segmentation approach as a decision-making tool for calculating premium prices and managing claim risk, according to experts. At the same time, it improves the insurance industry's competitiveness by making segmentation management more scientific.

Ina Maryani [4] proposed this paper to undertake customer segmentation on Nine Reload Credit using a data mining approach based on the RFM model and clustering techniques. The K-Means technique was used to create the clusters. With the Rapidminer 5.2 tools, K-Means creates a visual cluster model that uses RFM (Recency, Frequency, and Monetary) characteristics to indicate the amount of consumers in each cluster. Based on the RFM model, 102 customers were identified from the 82,648 transactions that were processed. Furthermore, we evaluated clusters using the K-Means approach, resulting in 63 consumers in Cluster 1 and 39 customers in Cluster 2.

III. MOTIVATION

Client segmentation might help marketers reach out to each customer in the most effective way possible. A customer segmentation study explores a large amount of data on customers (and potential customers) in order to correctly identify distinct groups of people based on demographic, behavioural, and other characteristics. Because a marketer's objective is to increase the value (revenue and/or profit) from each client, it's crucial to think about how each marketing action will effect the customer before implementing it. In an ideal world, "activity-centric" client

segmentation would highlight the long-term customer lifetime value (CLV) of a marketing action over its short-term value.

IV. METHODOLOGY

K-means clustering and hierarchical clustering are two of the most often utilised microarray data analysis clustering methods nowadays. However, each of these traditional clustering techniques has its own set of constraints.

A. K-Means Clustering

K-Means clustering is a common, quick, and effective clustering approach. M points in N dimensions are divided into K groups by the K-Means method (assuming k centroids). To achieve correct findings, these centroids must be properly established; otherwise, the conclusions may alter if the centroids' locations move. As a result, they must maintain the greatest feasible distance between them. After then, each data point is gathered and connected to the nearest centroid until no more data points can be found. This method produces an early grouping, after which k new centroids must be created to reflect the previous clusters' centres. The data points are clustered depending on their closeness to the centroids once the centroids have been calculated. The positions of the centroids are gradually adjusted in this iteration until no more changes are required and the positions of the centroids remain unchanged.

The K-Means algorithm is simple to understand. The centroids are the "K" cluster points that are placed in between the data points. The centroid with the shortest distance is assigned to each data point. Once each data item has been allocated, the centroids of the new groups are computed. The two steps are repeated until the centroid stops moving. This means that the objective function of having the smallest squared error has hit its limit and can no longer be improved. As a consequence, K clusters are obtained.

The K-Means Clustering technique is used on a pretty big dataset, and the results are shown. The dataset is based on mall customer data and includes seven attributes: ID, Sex, Marital Status, Age, Income, Occupation, and Settlement Size.

We can split the data points into four (4) clusters because we have a predetermined number of clusters. The mean values for the clusters may then be computed. Clusters 0,1,2,3 will likewise be renamed Better-off, Fewer Opportunities, Standard Living, and Career Oriented.

Because the K-Means approach requires the number of clusters, we will utilise the elbow methodology to determine the ideal number of clusters. The elbow approach [6] is used to find the ideal value of K in the K-means clustering methodology. This method finds the SSE of each data point with its nearest centroid for a variety of K values. The SSE reduces as the value of K rises, and the elbow, or the point at which we should stop dividing data further, is found at a given value of K where the SSE is lowest. In this situation, the

WCSS (Within-Cluster-Sum-of-Squared-Errors) metric is utilised as an indication. As a result, the "K" variable determines the number of clusters.

Figure 1 depicts the occurrence of an elbow point at K=5. After K=5, the difference in WCSS becomes less obvious. As

Fig. 1. A plot showing the K-means Clusters on the data points.

a consequence, we will select 5 clusters and use the K-Means approach to sort them.

Fig. 2. A plot showing the K-means Clusters on the data points.

Figure 2 shows a scatter plot of the clusters, with the X-axis representing age and the Y-axis representing income. As shown above, the data points in each cluster are coloured differently, with the centroids marked.

One of the most difficult challenges in cluster analysis is determining the number of clusters "K." As a result, this

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technique does not provide the ideal number of clusters, but this must be provided as input during clustering. The optimal number of clusters is one with the least variance among clusters and the most variation between clusters. One significant benefit of K-Means clustering is that its computational performance is faster than that of other hierarchical clustering algorithms and it is also simple to implement. According to, when the disparities between the categories are minimal and the data is scaled, this technique performs better; nevertheless, one significant disadvantage is that it is dependent on the original cluster centres. As a result, if these are chosen improperly, the results are likely to be erroneous and unstable.

B. Principal Component Analysis

As seen in Figure 2, if we just use two dimensions to illustrate the segmentation, it is difficult to distinguish the segments. Therefore, we must use PCA to cluster the data. PCA is a dimensionality-reduction methodology that condenses a large number of variables into a smaller set that maintains the majority of the information in the larger set. Naturally, reducing the number of variables in a data collection has an impact on accuracy; nevertheless, the solution to dimensionality reduction is to sacrifice some accuracy in return for more simplicity. Smaller data sets are easier to examine and demonstrate since machine learning algorithms can analyse data more easily and quickly without having to deal with superfluous factors. To summarise, the objective of PCA is to reduce dimensionality in a data set while keeping as much information as possible.

Fig. 3. K-means with PCA clustering.

We see the explained variance after fitting the PCA to our standardised data. We chose three components to describe our data, with more than 80% of the variation explained. We

obtain the loadings (i.e. correlations) of each component on each of the seven original characteristics after fitting our data with the chosen number of components.

Each component depicts a dimension of distinct features. Component 1: indicates career interests through income, occupation, and settlement size. Component 2: relates to gender, marital status, and education to indicate the individual's education and lifestyle. Component 3: relates marital status, age, and occupation to the amount of experience (worklife)

Fig. 4. A Scatter Plot showing the four(4) Segments.

Fig. 5. Hierarchical Clustering of the datapoint

A. Hierarchical Clustering

Hierarchical clustering [4] is a cluster analysis approach that aims to create a hierarchy of groups. A hierarchical clustering approach may be conceived of as a tree-structured collection

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of standard (flat) clustering algorithms. These techniques build clusters by recursively splitting the items either top-down or bottom-up. There are two types of strategies for this algorithm.

1) *Agglomerative* : A common example of HCA is the agglomerative hierarchical clustering method. The datasets are organised into clusters using the bottom-up approach. This means that this approach initially treats each dataset as a separate cluster and then begins merging the closest pair of clusters together. This process is continued until all of the clusters have been merged into a single cluster that contains all of the datasets.

2) *Divisive* : In Divisive Hierarchical Clustering, each data point is considered a distinct cluster, and the data points that are not comparable are separated from the cluster in each iteration. The split data points are handled as different clusters. Finally, there are N clusters. As a result, the amount and order of the data have an effect on the final outcomes. However, since the number of clusters is not required as an input to the method, we can have multiple partitioning groups, the choice of which is entirely up to the end user.

Figure 5 shows that there are smaller clusters within bigger clusters. These smaller groups have the same characteristics. We may pick the needed number of clusters from the dendrogram itself by selecting the maximum distance range and then drawing a cut-off line at that place. It merely implies that the space between the produced clusters is at its greatest and that differentiation may be made between them. As a consequence, according to Figure 3, we may select five clusters (K=5) for good results.

Because of its capacity to give visual results, hierarchical clustering has been widely used for segmentation.

The key benefit of hierarchical clustering is that the output is in the form of a hierarchy (dendrogram), which informs us exactly where the clusters joined or separated. By examining through the dendrogram, we can easily determine and decide on the amount of clusters to take. However, for a high number of observations, its computing speed is quite slow when compared to nonhierarchical clustering algorithms.

V. CONCLUSION

Consumer data is growing at an exponential rate as a result of increased commercialization. Businesses must use more effective clustering algorithms for client segmentation when dealing with such large amounts of data. These clustering models must be able to analyse this large amount of data properly. Each of the above-mentioned clustering approaches has its own set of benefits and drawbacks. In terms of processing performance, K-Means clustering is far faster than hierarchical clustering techniques, which require the whole proximity matrix to be created after each iteration. With a large number of observations, K-Means clustering performs better, although hierarchical clustering can tolerate fewer data points.

The most challenging task is determining the number of clusters "K" required for the K-Means procedure, which must be submitted as an input to this non-hierarchical clustering method. Because no cluster centres are required as input, this limitation does not apply to hierarchical clustering. The cluster groups and their number must be chosen by the user. When using a randomly generated dataset, hierarchical clustering outperforms K-Means. Dendrograms are produced via hierarchical clustering, whereas K-Means produces flat-structured clusters that are difficult to analyse. In comparison to K-Means clustering, the quality (accuracy) of hierarchical clustering improves as k increases. As a result, big datasets benefit from partitioning methods like K-Means, whilst small datasets benefit from hierarchical clustering algorithms. K-Means and Hierarchical Clustering both have flaws that make them inappropriate for usage on their own. Data

visualisation, which is an important aspect of effective data processing in business, is aided by hierarchical clustering. In addition, when performance is considered, K-Means tends to produce superior outcomes. Given the drawbacks and advantages of both techniques, it's clear that integrating the best of both algorithms might surpass the separate models. Finally, because of their preference for different types of data, many clustering methods can be used in succession, maximising the benefits of these approaches. However, the effective selection of these techniques, as well as their sensible execution, may need a large time investment in data acquisition and processing, as well as a thorough understanding of the objectives and requirements.

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